

CARDIAC ISCHEMIA

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Annotation. The article covers the etiology, pathogenesis, classification, diagnosis, clinical picture and treatment of myocardial infarction, provides a literature review and describes the structure of the incidence of myocardial infarction.

Keywords: myocardial infarction, etiology, pathogenesis, cardiovascular complications.

ETIOLOGY

The development of myocardial infarction is based on unexpected thrombosis of the coronary artery in the area where there is an atherosclerotic plaque with a blocked artery. According to world statistics, atherosclerosis of the arteries is already observed at 45-50 years of age. The origin of a thrombus is based on the fact that at the site of rupture of the "cap" of the plaque, an accumulation of mediators occurs (serotonin, ADP, platelet activating factor and platelet aggregation factor), which begin to stimulate subsequent platelet aggregation and mechanical narrowing of the coronary artery (CA). This process is dynamic and can take on various forms. In addition to coronary artery thrombosis, the following etiology is distinguished: concomitant diseases (these include type 2 diabetes mellitus, other endocrinological pathology), there is also a history of arterial hypertension, and coronary heart disease. If a patient has a myocardial infarction with a pathological Q wave, the likely cause is occlusion of the coronary arteries, if a myocardial infarction without a pathological Q wave occurs most often with spontaneous restoration of perfusion. Hyperlipidemia (patients' diets include excessive consumption of foods high in fat, which increases the content of LDL and HDL, which can lead to thrombosis), large amounts of alcohol consumption contributes to the development of myocardial muscle necrosis, smoking (over 20 years of experience), low physical activity, obesity (abdominal obesity), all these factors contribute to the development of myocardial infarction, psycho-emotional stress or mental tension also contributes to the development.

PATHOGENESIS

The pathogenesis of myocardial infarction is based on the following mechanisms, one of them: rupture of an atherosclerotic plaque, which is provoked by a sudden increase in the sympathetic nervous system (a sharp increase in blood pressure occurs, a sharp increase in heart rate (HR), and an increase in coronary circulation). The second mechanism is the formation of a blood clot at the site of a ruptured atherosclerotic plaque. A thrombus is formed due to increased platelet aggregation and activation of the coagulant system. There are three stages of thrombus that obliterate the coronary artery. 1) Hemorrhage occurs into the plaque 2) Formation of an intravascular non-occlusive thrombus 3) Distribution of the thrombus until the vessel is completely blocked. Pathomorphological changes in myocardial infarction: 1. Damage to the main coronary artery with its blockage is accompanied by transmural necrosis (as a rule). 2. For non-transmural infarctions, damage to several arteries is more typical, which does not reach complete occlusion and is accompanied by "clustered" necrosis of myocardiocytes. 3. Isolated damage to the right ventricle occurs only in 5% of patients and even less frequently, mainly in patients with chronic cor pulmonale. 4. Necrotic damage to the atria is observed in 17% of those who died from myocardial infarction; damage to the right atrium is more common. 5. Isolated atrial myocardial infarction refers to casuistry.

CLASSIFICATION OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

Acute myocardial infarction (duration less than 4 weeks after acute onset): acute transmural infarction of the anterior myocardial wall; acute transmural infarction of the lower myocardial wall; acute transmural infarction of other specified localizations; / acute transmural infarction of unspecified localization; acute subendocardial myocardial infarction; acute myocardial infarction, unspecified.

Clinical classification of myocardial infarction

1) Anginal form: this form is typical of myocardial infarction, it is characterized by the appearance of intense compressive pain behind the sternum, lasting 30 minutes, which is not relieved by nitroglycerin. In addition to all this, pain radiates to the left half of the chest, jaw, and also to the back, to the area of the shoulder blade; there is also a pain syndrome, which is accompanied by fear of death and weakness, sweating is possible. 2) Asthmatic form: with this form, shortness of breath and suffocation appear, the patient assumes an orthopneic

position, pain is absent or less pronounced. 3) Abdominal form: this form is characterized by localized pain in the epigastric region, dyspeptic syndrome is noted (hiccoughs, belching, nausea, and vomiting), there may also be bloating, pain is present, pain irradiates usually to the back in the area of the scapula. 4) Arrhythmic form: this form is characterized by palpitations, no pain syndrome, possible development of weakness, and disturbance of cerebral blood flow due to reduced blood pressure may be observed. 5) Cerebrovascular form: this form is characterized by symptoms of cerebral ischemia - headache, dizziness, fainting, vomiting; there is disorientation in space. There may also be the development of tachycardia and bradyarrhythmia.

CLINICAL PICTURE

In the clinical picture of myocardial infarction, the following important periods of development of clinical symptoms are distinguished: the first period is the most acute period, this period is characterized by the appearance of signs of myocardial necrosis, as well as clinical symptoms, the time for ischemia to occur is up to 2 hours or 30 minutes. The second period is the acute period, this period is characterized by the formation of an area of necrosis, the duration of which is up to 10 days. The third period is the subacute period, this period is characterized by the completion of the organization of the scar, which begins on the 10th day and lasts until the end of 4-8 weeks. The fourth period is the post-infarction period, this period is characterized by the fact that the scar density increases, and the myocardial muscle also adapts to new conditions, that is, the cardiovascular system begins to function differently, this period lasts from 2 to 6 months.

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